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Project families: How to improve learning in thesis works and increase impact on research

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INTRODUCTION

A university has a number of activities, of which teaching and research are the two most important and dominating activities, often in competition for the resources. Thesis work is an important but also resource requiring activity during the education, in which the students demonstrate their true competences, apply what they have learned and solve problems without a textbook solution. In doing that they typically work one or two students together on stand-alone projects, a concept which often stress both students and supervisors and which requires much support, in particular if they have experimental activities. It is, therefore, relevant to improve the concept of the thesis activities and to consider the following questions

- Can we identify the most important key competences for the candidates ?
- Is the level of the candidates competences sufficient ?
- Can we increase the students learning outcome and generic skills in their thesis projects?
- Can we increase the students' contribution to research and innovation?

This paper describes learning outcomes, generic skills developed by the students and the scientific impact with applying the concept, project families, in thesis work.

1. THE KEY COMPETENCES

Identifying the most important key competences is extremely important for a university, in order to focus the teaching and learning correctly. DTU Civil Engineering was in 2009 [1] inspired by an earlier investigation carried out for MIT in 2001 among faculty, young candidates and their employers [2], to identify the most important key competences for MIT graduates. The DTU investigation used questionnaires and interviews of the young candidates and their employers and identified the three most important competences as: 1) Engineering reasoning and problem solving, 2) Communication (oral and written) and 3) Personal skills and attitudes (initiative, thinking, critical, creative and flexible). The MIT investigation and others [3], [4], [5], [6] found similar priorities of the competences in the period 1988 to 2016.

The educations at Danish universities are all under an accreditation system, where each education is reviewed every 3 or 6 years. A part of this accreditation is a review of candidate quality, where the reviews have confirmed that our candidate competence level is very good and even increasing.

2. THE PROJECT FAMILY CONCEPT

The authors decided to develop and test a new concept for the thesis work to support the learning of the key competences more efficient [7], [8] than the traditional thesis project, where a group of 1 or 2 students working on a stand-alone project with a supervisor. The traditional projects are always problem-based and benefits from the advantages, known from problem and project-based learning and includes many CDIO aspects, but have weaknesses due to the very individual work activities, where peer interaction or cooperation rarely occur and many resources are spend on very basic problems.

The new concept aims at both improving the students learning and increasing their contribution to research and innovation by focusing a group of student projects at a common research topic, where a research group form a supervisor team. This concept intend to support an increase in voluntary peer-interactions and collaboration and to create an improved base for a good project flow. The reformed concept is called the **project family** concept.

The project families may deal with different parts of a larger problem or they may deal with the same problem, defined by the supervision team. The students specify their project statement individually, so each project is still unique, which still is a requirement. However, the projects in the family are encouraged to cooperate and they may even use each other's results (with references).

The formative assessment is based on a midterm conference where each project presents their results so far to the project family, the supervisors and often representatives from the industry, as well as the peer interactions at the supervisor meetings. The summative assessment of the projects are the same as for the rest of the departments' students (reference group), which is an oral presentation with an external censor and on a written report.

The authors have over the years 2011-2017 tried the project family concept with 104 Civil Engineering students (26 BEng students, 49 BSc students and 26 MSc students) in 14 project families. The project families have varied in size and have consisted of between 4 and 16. The project families may consist of a mixture of BEng, BSc and MSc projects with different basic knowledge, learning levels and number of ECTS points. The project families have been until now been organised under three different research areas with different supervision teams at the department:

- ZeroWaste: Focus is on utilising waste materials as secondary raw materials.
- Glass structures: Focus is on use of glass as a load-carrying structural material.
- Strengthening of structures: Focus is on strengthening of concrete beams.

Due to the difference in the research topics and their maturity and the personal style of the supervisors, the supervision concept for the project families vary slightly. The supervisions schemes are shown in Table 1.

Action	ZeroWaste	Glass	Strengthening
Start-up meeting	X	X	X
Weekly project family meeting with all students, main supervisor and relevant co-supervisors	X	X	Only first month
Time required for weekly project family meeting	½-1 hour	1 hour	1,5-2 hours
Individual meetings	If required	No	After first month
Project status at every project family meeting	X	X	X
Task groups formed during the period for dealing with different challenges.	No	X	X
Group instruction in experimental procedures	X	X	X
Group instruction in special computer programs	Not required	X	Not required
Sharing experimental facility	X	If experimenting	X
Midterm presentation (poster based) and discussion about further project activities	X	X	No
Sharing a joint room for all students	X	X	X

Table 1. Overview of supervision and sharing of facilities.

3. THE STUDENTS BENEFITS

3.1. Grades of the projects

It is difficult to measure the direct effect on the grouping of projects in project families on each of the three key competences; Engineering reasoning and problem solving, 2) Communication and 3) Personal skills and attitudes, individually. The combined effects, however, can be documented by comparing the grades earned by the project family members with the grades of the students conducting their thesis work in traditional stand-alone projects (reference group).

The reference group consisted of the BEng (338), BSc (159) and MSc (395) Civil Engineering students, who carried out their thesis work at DTU Civil Engineering during 2012-16 and represents the same educations as in the project families. The weights of the three educations are set to their relative numbers in the project families, just as similar weights will be used in all other comparisons (Figures 1 and 2 and Tables 2, 3 and 4) in this paper in order to have as representative a reference group as possible.

Figure 1. Distribution of thesis grades 2012-2017, Danish grades in brackets.

Figure 2. Accumulated distribution of average grades during their education.

Figure 1 show that the grades are better in the project families, than in the corresponding reference group. Figure 2 illustrates that the variations of their average grades during the studies are very similar in the project family group and in the reference group.

The grades for the different Civil Engineering educations are shown in Table 2, where it can be seen that the project families have lead to a statistically significant increase of the thesis grades, regardless of the education (significant defined as a confidence level of 95% and simulated using a Monte Carlo simulation). The statistical significantly results are marked with * in Tables 2 to 4.

It can be seen from Table 3, that it is especially the below average students, who significantly improve, but that the improvements are observed for all groups except the top 25 % performing students.

Table 4 shows that projects within all three research and supervision groups have resulted in improvements of grades, compared with the reference group. The data for

the reference group in Table 4 is a combination of the data for the three educations, weighted corresponding to their numbers of students in the project family.

Type of education	Project families			Reference group		
	Education	Thesis	No	Education	Thesis	No
BEng	7.1	10.9*	26	7.7	9.7	338
BSc	8.1	10.8*	49	8.1	10.2	159
MSc	9.0	11.1*	27	8.7	10.2	395
All	8.1	10.9*	104	8.1	10.1	892

Table 2. Average grades for students in their education and in their thesis, grouped after their education.

Average in education	Project families			Reference group		
	Education	Thesis	No	Education	Thesis	No
Below 7	6.3	10.0*	22	6.1	8.3	227
7 to 8	7.4	10.9	28	7.5	10.0	196
8 to 9	8.5	11.1	26	8.5	10.8	178
Above 9	9.8	11.5	28	10.0	11.5	291

Table 3. Average grades for students during their educations and in their thesis, grouped according to their average grades in their educations.

Project family	Project families			Reference group	
	Education	Thesis	No	Education	Thesis
ZeroWaste	7.8	11.0*	57	8.0	9.9
Glass	8.5	10.7	33	8.4	10.2
Strengthening	8.4	11.1	14	8.3	10.0

Table 4. Average grades for students in their educations and in their thesis, grouped after research area and supervision team.

3.2. The students experiences

A number of questionnaires were issued to the students in 2014 (11 of 14 students answered) and in 2017 (15 of 23 students answered), asking them about their experiences, dealing with supervision, peer-interaction, their work situation and how they rate their own performances. The sums of the responses are shown on Figures 3 and 4.

Figure 3. Question to the student: How was the supervision ? (Mark all you agree with).

Figure 4. Question: How the students experienced the work in a project family (Mark all you agree with).

Figure 5. Question: How did the project family concept affect your achievements ? (mark only one).

The Figures 3 to 5 show, that the students appreciated the concept of project families, that they interacted well and had more fun and that they felt that they achieved more than if they had worked on a stand-alone project. Some of the students added qualitative comments to their questionnaires or to a later interview [9], where one students stated:

" When you are in a project family, you have more angles to your work, You achieve more on less time, because you are constantly challenged in your way of thinking. If you work alone, that will be slower"

THE UNIVERSITY'S BENEFITS

3.3. The supervisors experiences

The supervisors found that the supervision required for basic instructions was the same for a project family as for a single, traditional stand-alone project, although individual supervision was still used in addition to this. The students are better prepared for the project family supervision meetings, than for the traditional projects and the supervisors spend less time on basic activities. This allowed the student projects to progress to a deeper level and the learning process and the supervision could deal with deeper and more advanced topics, as both students and supervisor had room for the more advanced experiments and discussions and thus improving their use of engineering reasoning and problem solving.

The quality of the students' planning, their input for supervision and not least their oral and written communication and technical vocabulary have been significantly

improved, just as a much larger number of the thesis reports are useful for the supervisors' research. The larger number of students in a project family has also the benefit, that the supervision group can actually plan for a project family to have a substantial input to their research. The project family concept has also significantly reduced the number of reports, which could not be used in research due to lack of proper reporting. These improvements are difficult to indicate numbers for, but the reported grades illustrate the improvements clearly, as the summative assessment has not changed.

The results from the project families have been used in 14 publications in conference proceedings and scientific journals or as "pilot" or "screening" testing in the research areas. The use of the project results depends much on the type of scientific area and the maturity of the research area in which the students participate.

An additional benefit of the use of project families is a more rational use of the laboratory resources, where a 25-75% reduction of the hours used for instructing and supporting the students has been estimated by the laboratory leaders. They report also that the students are better prepared for and behave more professional in their laboratory work and thus learn more and faster, just as they observe an increased peer-interaction by the project family students compared to the reference group students and that the project family students even instruct and correct each other in the laboratories. The students have in their work and in their interaction with the supervisors and the laboratory staff shown a marked improvement in their personal skills and attitude, which appears much more professional and mature than previously.

4. SUMMARY AND PERSPECTIVES

The use of project families improves learning outcome and grades and increase the quantitative input to the research activities. The improvements on grades are largest for the below average students when making their thesis project in a project family, whose performances were improved to match the performance of the above average students in the reference group. No effect has, however, been observed among the top level students (with grades among the best 25 % performing students), probably because these would normally obtain an A(12) for their thesis work.

The use of project families requires the supervisor and laboratory leaders to plan ahead of the projects initiation, to secure the necessary allocation of staff, equipment and facilities. The concept reduce the resources required for basic supervision and laboratory support and allows the resources (from students, supervisors and technicians) to be used for deeper learning and creates a better project experiences for all involved.

The size of the project family should be between 6 and 10, as fewer leads to too little peer-interaction and little benefit and larger families tend to split into several subfamilies, who work independently of each other.

The project family concept is already being used in other research areas at the authors department (experiences from these areas will be collected and evaluated) and it is expected that it will in the future also be tested in project families, consisting entirely of theoretical projects with no experimental activities.

The concept will be further developed in cooperation with new projects students. The concept and its long-term effects will also be evaluated through interviews with former students, who has graduated less than five years ago, in order to evaluate how these additional competences have influenced their performance in the industry.

The concept is also expected to be used in classic courses, where experimental activities or results will be introduced in order to support an understanding and a critical evaluation of the students own predictions and to support an increased use of the experimental facilities.

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